

STEROID COMPOUNDS. PART II. ON A ROUTE TO THE SYNTHESIS OF STEREOCHEMICALLY HOMOGENEOUS STEROID KETONES*

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Addition of HCN to the $\alpha\beta$ -double bond of Hagemann's ester, followed by alcoholysis, reduction and hydrolysis affords exclusively *trans*-1-methylcyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylic acid. The exclusive formation of the "*trans*" isomer suggests that the addition to the double bond pursues a single course. The reactions have been extended to the dicyclic analogue of Hagemann's ester, where the products also appear to be stereochemically homogeneous. The possibility of the application of this method for the synthesis of steroid ketones with "*trans*" fusion of the rings B/C and C/D has been pointed out.

In Part I of this series (Mukharji, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **24**, 91), a method for the synthesis of steroid skeleton with the two angular methyl groups has been described. This method, although useful for the construction of skeletons corresponding to the formula of the natural steroid compounds, as they are written on the paper, is not, however, in the least suitable for the ultimate total synthesis of the compounds of this group. On account of the presence of a large number of asymmetric centres in the steroid molecule, and consequently the possibility of the existence of a large number of isomers, which are structurally the same but stereochemically different, the synthetic approach in this field is a very formidable task. This aspect of the problem has been discussed by Robinson in the following language in a very recent publication (Cornforth and Robinson, *Nature*, 1947, **160**, 737) "...The outcome has been that the structures of the chief members of the rapidly expanding family of substances are known in so far as that is possible without the final confirmation of successful synthesis. The latter task has been regarded as one of the most difficult that can be undertaken by the organic chemist for the simple reason that it is far from sufficient to devise a method of constructing a substance corresponding to the formula as written on the paper, difficult though that may be in itself. The molecule of dihydrocholesterol contains 9 asymmetric carbon atoms and hence 512 stereoisomers are possible. There is reason to believe that all these should be capable of existence. Even if the side-chain is not present and the position C₁₇ (steroid numbering) carries a carbonyl group there are still 128 stereoisomeric forms".

It is thus evident that unless suitable precautions are taken to prevent the formation of isomers at the intermediate stages of synthesis, the final product will invariably contain a mixture of a large number of stereoisomers. The isolation of the individuals from such a mixture involving the tedious process of fractional crystallisation is no doubt a very difficult task, which may not even succeed to the desired extent if the number of isomers in the mixture is large. And finally, although the separation of the individual isomers may be achieved, a definite characterisation of the stereoisomers still remains a very complicated problem.

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In all the known steroids the rings B/C and C/D are fused in the *trans* position ; variations occur only in respect of the fusion of the rings A and B, which are fused in the *cis* position (Coprosterol, bile acids) or in the *trans* position (dihydrocholesterol, androsterone) in various derivatives.

A new synthetic route has now been investigated in a number of preliminary experiments and this route possesses the important feature, that not only can the stereochemical vagaries be placed under the maximum control, but the products may possibly consist almost completely, if not wholly, of only one single stereoisomer, the stereochemical nature of which can be ascertained to a fair extent from the method of its formation. The preliminary experiments, so far carried out with simpler systems, show that the reactions that will be employed in the actual synthesis of the steroid ketones, rather remarkably lead to stereochemically homogeneous intermediates which belong to the stereochemical series of the desired type. From such intermediates the synthesis of the tetracyclic systems will follow conventional route, which has been pointed out later on.

Ethyl 4-keto-2-methyl- $\Delta^{2:3}$ -cyclohexen-1-carboxylate, Hagemann's ester (I) (Hagemann, *Ber.*, 1893, 26, 876; Rouault and Smith, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 631) smoothly adds up the elements of hydrocyanic acid to the $\alpha\beta$ -double bond (cf. Lapworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 950) to yield the nitrile (II), which has been converted into the corresponding keto-diester (III, R=Et) by treatment with alcoholic hydrogen chloride (cf. Pfeiffer and Matton, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 1113). Considerable difficulty has been encountered in all attempts for the direct conversion of the keto-nitrile (II) into the corresponding keto-diacid (III, R=H); treatment with concentrated hydrochloric acid or with a mixture of concentrated sulphuric acid and acetic acid under a variety of experimental conditions proved futile. The keto-diester (III, R=Et) has been reduced with amalgamated zinc and alcoholic hydrogen chloride (cf. Schneider and Spielman, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1942, 142, 351), and the resulting diester (IV) on hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid furnishes *trans*-1-methylcyclohexane-1:2-dicarboxylic acid (V) (Linstead and Millidge, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 478; Bachmann and Kushner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 1963), which is also obtained directly when the above keto-diester (III, R=Et) is reduced with amalgamated zinc and concentrated hydrochloric acid according to conventional Clemmensen procedure. The melting point of the above dicarboxylic acid (V) is not depressed when mixed with an authentic specimen of *trans*-1-methylcyclohexane-1:2-dicarboxylic acid.* It is of considerable interest to note here that in this synthesis only the *trans* isomeride of the acid is formed exclusively; the simultaneous formation of some *cis* form of the acid has not been observed so far. The homogeneous nature of the dicarboxylic acid (V), thus obtained, suggests that the addition of HCN to the $\alpha\beta$ -double bond (I) proceeds in an uniform manner to yield the nitrile (II) where the CN and the CO₂Et groups are also placed obviously in the *trans* position. The preferential and almost exclusive formation of the *trans* isomer in this synthesis is probably to be attributed to the steric influence of the carbethoxyl group in (I) and also perhaps to the repulsive action between this carbethoxyl group and the incoming cyano group, both of which are negative in character. It may be mentioned here that in all previous syn-

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theses of 1-methylcyclohexane-1:2-dicarboxylic acid (Linstead and Millidge, *loc. cit.* Bachmann and Kushner, *loc. cit.*) a mixture of the *cis* and the *trans* isomers has invariably been obtained, which are separated by repeated crystallisation.

In an analogous manner, the dicyclic analogue of Hagemann's ester, ethyl *trans*-4-keto-2-methyl- $\Delta^{2:3}$ -octahydronaphthalene-1-carboxylate (VI, Barret, Cook and Linstead, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1066) smoothly adds up HCN to the $\alpha\beta$ -double bond to yield the keto-nitrile (VII). This has been obtained as colourless silky needles, m. p. 116°-17°, and appears to be stereochemically pure. Treatment with alcoholic hydrogen chloride furnishes the corresponding keto-diester (VIII, R=Et) as a highly viscous liquid. Now, the probable factors which govern the course of addition of HCN to the $\alpha\beta$ -double bond are identical in both the cases (I and VI), because the relative disposition of the grouping

is the same in each case. It may reasonably be concluded therefore that the CN and the CO₂Et groups in the dicyclic compound (VII) are also placed in the *trans* position, as has been proved to be the case in the monocyclic derivative (II).

(IX)

(X)

Now, even accepting that the two rings and the CN and CO₂Et groups in the dicyclic keto-nitrile (VII) occur in the *trans* configuration, two isomerides of the compound (VII) are still possible depending upon the orientation of the methyl group and one of the angular hydrogen atoms as represented in figures (IX) and (X). In view of this possibility, the keto-nitrile (VII) has been subjected to careful fractional crystallisation. So far the product appears to be quite homogeneous, only the one particular form (m. p. 116°-17°) mentioned earlier has been obtained. It is quite likely that the other possible form is also present simultaneously in smaller amounts and has escaped detection. When larger quantities of the substance is available, it is hoped to reinvestigate this question.

Extension of the above reactions to the tricyclic keto-esters (XIII) and (XIV), which are analogous to Hagemann's ester, will eventually lead to the formation of the tricyclic dicarboxylic acids (XV) and (XVI), with the two carboxyl groups most likely in the *trans* position. By preferential double homologation of the secondary carboxyl group, followed by Dieckmann condensation of the adipate, the cyclopentane ring (ring D) can be smoothly developed being fused in the *trans* position with the ring C. This part of the scheme is similar to the method employed by Bachmann for the synthesis of *trans*-8-methylhydrindanone from *trans*-1-methylcyclohexane-1:2-dicarboxylic acid (Bachmann and Kushner, *loc. cit.*).

The required tricyclic keto-esters (XIII) and (XIV) with *trans* fusion of the rings B/C can be readily prepared from the $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketones (XI) and (XII) and ethyl acetoacetate, following the method of preparing ethyl *trans*-4-keto-2-methyl- $\Delta^{2:3}$ -octahydronaphthalene-1-carboxylate (VI) from acetylcyclohexene and ethyl acetoacetate (cf. Barrett, Cook and Linstead, *loc. cit.* See Part III, this issue, p.373).

(XI)

(XIII)

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Ethyl 4-Keto-2-methyl- $\Delta^{2:3}$ -cyclohexen-1-carboxylate (Hagemann's ester) was prepared essentially following the procedure described by Rouault and Smith (*loc. cit.*), but a smaller amount of piperidine was employed than that recommended by the above authors. The reaction proceeded with equal facility when this slight modification was introduced and the yield of the final product was unaffected. The following proportion of the reactants were used: ethyl acetoacetate (156 g.), *para*formaldehyde (18 g.) and piperidine (4 c.c.). The average yield was 54-56 g.

Ethyl 3-Methyl-3-cyanocyclohexanone-4-carboxylate (II).—A solution of Hagemann's ester (28.5 g.) in rectified spirit (100 c.c.), cooled in an ice-bath, was treated with a solution of potassium cyanide (21.3 g.) in water (52 c.c.). To the yellow solution, after standing for 30 minutes, glacial acetic acid (9.8 g.) was added from a dropping funnel the end of which reached the bottom of the liquid. The reaction mixture was left overnight (20-24 hours) in a refrigerator. The brown solution was poured into water and extracted with ether and the extract was washed twice with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue after removal of ether was fractionated under reduced pressure. After a forerun of the unreacted Hagemann's ester, the hydrocyanic acid addition product distilled between 130° and 145°/3 mm., which on redistillation boiled at 135°-138°/3 mm. as a pale yellow, mobile liquid, yield 12 g. Found: N, 6.1, 6.77. C₁₁H₁₅O₃N requires N, 6.7 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* of the nitrile crystallised from alcohol in clusters of glistening needles, m. p. 206°: (Found: N, 22.0. C₁₂H₁₈O₃N₁ requires N, 21.05 per cent).

Ethyl 3-Methylcyclohexanone-3:4-dicarboxylate (III, R = Et).—The above keto-nitrile (II, 8 g.), dissolved in absolute alcohol (30 c.c.), was treated with alcohol (10 c.c.)

saturated with dry hydrogen chloride gas at 0° . The mixture was left overnight at the ordinary temperature and then refluxed on a steam-bath for 5 to 6 hours. Ammonium chloride separated at the bottom of the flask. The solution was then poured into cold water and the oil taken up in ether. The ether extract was washed with dilute bicarbonate of soda solution, water and dried. The residue left on removal of the ether was distilled and the fraction boiling between 130° and $140^{\circ}/3$ mm. was collected. On redistillation, it boiled at 135° - $137^{\circ}/3$ mm. as a colourless, mobile liquid, yield 4 g. A higher boiling residue was left in the distilling flask. (Found: C, 61.7; H, 8.0. $C_{13}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 60.94; H, 7.81 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* was crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol, m. p. 158° . (Found: N, 13.59. $C_{14}H_{23}O_3N_3$ requires N, 13.41 per cent).

Ethyl 1-Methylcyclohexane-1:2-dicarboxylate (IV).—The above keto-ester (3.5 g.), dissolved in absolute alcohol (20 c.c.), was taken in a flask containing amalgamated zinc (18 g.). Absolute alcohol (30 c.c.), saturated with dry hydrogen chloride at 0° , was then added to the above solution. After the initial vigour of the reaction was over, the flask was heated on a water-bath for about 6 hours, and again alcoholic hydrogen chloride (15 c.c.) was added and the heating continued for 18 hours more. The solution was then poured into cold water and extracted with ether. The ether extract was then washed with dilute bicarbonate of soda solution, water and dried. The oil left on evaporation of the ether was distilled under diminished pressure, when the dihydro-ester distilled at 107° - $109^{\circ}/3$ mm. as a colourless, mobile liquid, yield 2.5 g. (Found: C, 64.18; H, 8.92. $C_{13}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 64.46; H, 9.1 per cent).

trans-1-Methylcyclohexane-1:2-dicarboxylic Acid (V).—The above ester (2 g.) was boiled under reflux with concentrated hydrochloric acid (40 c.c.) for 24 hours. The acid separated from the cold solution in colourless sandy crystals which after drying was crystallised from hot water containing a little acetone, m. p. 213° , with previous softening at 210° . The mixed melting point with an authentic specimen of *trans-1-methylcyclohexane-1:2-dicarboxylic acid* was not depressed. (Found: C, 57.98; H, 7.8. $C_9H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 58.06; H, 7.5 per cent).

The *trans-acid* was also obtained when the above keto-ester (III, R=Et, 1 g.) was reduced with amalgamated zinc (5 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.) for 20 hours with the addition of a little hydrochloric acid from time to time. The acid was isolated in the usual manner and crystallised from hot water containing a little acetone, m. p. 213° .

Ethyl trans-4-keto-2-methyl- $\Delta^{2:8}$ -octahydronaphthalene-1-carboxylate (VI) was prepared from acetylcyclohexene and ethyl sodioacetoacetate following the description of Barrett, Cook and Linstead (*loc. cit.*); however, with the slight variation described here a better yield was attained.

Acetylcyclohexene required for this purpose was prepared from cyclohexene nitrile and methylmagnesium iodide following the condition of Butenandt and Schmidt-Thome (*Ber.*, 1938, 71, 1487). To a Grignard reagent prepared from magnesium (10.5 g.),

methyl iodide (36 c. c.) and dry ether (200 c. c.), *cyclohexene* nitrile (45 g.) was added dropwise in the course of about 15 minutes. The ether was then gradually distilled off and replaced by dry benzene (150 c. c.), and the solution refluxed on a steam-bath for 6 hours. After cooling, glacial acetic acid (45 c. c.) was gradually added and the mixture refluxed for 30 minutes. Water was then added and the solution heated for 30 minutes more. The benzene layer was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue from the benzene solution was distilled under reduced pressure, when acetyl*cyclohexene* came over at 80-82°/9 mm., yield 28 g.

To the sodio salt, prepared from ethyl acetoacetate (30 g.), sodium (4.6 g.) and absolute alcohol (60 c. c.), cooled in a freezing mixture, acetyl*cyclohexene* (24 g.) was added and the mixture left as such at the room temperature for three days. It was then heated on a steam-bath for 3 hours. After removing the excess of alcohol, the mixture was decomposed with glacial acetic acid and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with cold dilute caustic soda solution; water and dried. Ether was then evaporated off and the residue distilled under reduced pressure. The condensation product distilled at 180°/9 mm. as a pale yellow liquid, yield 16 g.

Ethyl 3-Methyl-3-cyanodecalone-4-carboxylate (VII).—A solution of ethyl *trans*-4-keto-2-methyl- $\Delta^{2:3}$ -octahydronaphthalene-1-carboxylate (10 g.) in rectified spirit (50 c. c.) was treated with a solution of potassium cyanide (6 g.) in water (15 c. c.), followed by the addition of glacial acetic acid (2.5 c. c.) exactly in the manner described earlier. After allowing the reaction mixture to remain in the refrigerator for about 30 hours, it was worked up in the usual manner and distilled. After careful removal of the unreacted material, the addition product (VII) was collected between 175° and 185°/1.5 mm. distilling almost constantly at 176°-178°/1.5 mm. as an almost colourless viscous liquid. The product did not solidify when left as such in a vacuum desiccator, but on trituration with a little alcohol the nitrile very readily solidified. It crystallised from methyl alcohol in beautiful, colourless, silky needles, m. p. 116-117°, yield 3 g. (Found: N, 5.16. $C_{17}H_{21}O_3N$ requires N, 5.32 per cent).

The nitrile was subjected to careful fractional crystallisation but so far the product appeared to be quite homogeneous.

Ethyl 3-Methyldecalone-3:4-dicarboxylate (VIII, R=Et).—The above crystalline keto-nitrile (2.5 g.), dissolved in absolute alcohol (10 c. c.), was treated with alcohol (20 c. c.), saturated with dry hydrogen chloride gas at 0°, and left overnight. Next day, it was refluxed for 10 hours on a steam-bath when separation of ammonium chloride took place. The resulting keto-ester was worked up in the usual manner and it distilled at 178°-182°/2 mm. as a colourless, highly viscous liquid. (Found: C, 66.38; H, 8.7. $C_{17}H_{26}O_2$ requires C, 65.81; H, 8.4 per cent).

The keto-ester (1 g.) was heated under reflux on a wire gauze for about 30 hours with amalgamated zinc (25 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c. c.); small quantities of hydrochloric acid (30 c. c. in all) was added to the above solution from time to time. The solution was then extracted with ether after saturation with ammonium chloride. The extract was then extracted twice with dilute bicarbonate of soda solution. The

bicarbonate extract was then very carefully acidified, when a solid together with a little adhering oil separated. After drying overnight in a vacuum desiccator, the acid was first crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether mixture and then twice from hot water containing a little acetone. m. p. 202-204°. (Found : C, 61.81 ; H, 7.51. $C_{13}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 61.41 ; H, 7.1 per cent. $C_{13}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 65.0 ; H, 8.3 per cent). The acid is probably the keto-dicarboxylic acid (VIII, R=H), the carbonyl group having escaped reduction.

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